

Emergence of Proto-Communication using Action Primitives Symbolized in Recurrent Q-Learning Agents

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Abstract: In this paper, we suppose the gesture theory that is one of the theories on the origin of language, which tries to establish that the speech originated from gestures. Based on the theory, we assume that “actions” having some purposes can be used as “symbols” in the communication through a learning process. The purpose of this study is to clarify what abilities of agents are necessary to acquire usages of the actions as the symbols. To achieve the purpose, we adopt a collision avoidance game and recurrent Q-learning (RQL) agents as the game players. Our simulations showed that the RQL agents can emerge a proto-communication to avoid collision with opponent by using visual information that the opponent turns its own eye away from the agent through the learning process. Further, we found that the RQL agents also obtain a rotational behavior to avoid collision by expanding the maximum number of learning iteration.

Keywords: Collision Avoidance Game; Emergence of Proto-Communication; Neural Q-Learning (NQL) Agents; Recurrent Q-Learning (RQL) Agents; Symbolization of Action Primitives

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, we are communicating with each other by using various media such as voices, characters, and gestures. A proto-communication, however, would have been simpler than the present communication. How does the communication emerge and evolve to complex form like a current one? To the above questions, Corballis [1] and Tomasello [2] claim that gestures using hands and arms precede voices in the evolution of communication. In this paper, we discuss about emergence of communication by gestures based on the assertion.

There are many researches concerning the emergence of communication. Takano and Arita [3] conducted an evolutionary simulation experiment in which agents play a collision avoidance game. The evolutionary simulation showed that the agents emerged cooperative behaviors to inform collision avoidance behaviors through mutual refusing eye contacts, although no rewards have been given for the success of the communication. The action primitive refusing eye contact can be regarded as a symbol to establish such communication. In the emergence of the actual communication; however, we think that some methods and knowledge to need for the success of the

communication do not have congenitally and are obtained by a heuristic learning after birth.

Unlike the research of Takano and Arita [3], Shirasaki and Sato [4] adopted the collision avoidance task with simple Q-learning agents [5], but an action using eyesight to avoid collision with opponents was not observed. The reason why this result was given can be presumed that the environmental information given to the agents are discretized in the Q-learning [5], and differences of important states to achieve the agents' aims can be overlooked by the discretization.

Moreover, Sato [5] adopted a modified model of Shirasaki and Sato [4] which can take into account the past information earned from the opponents, and confirmed that more appropriate behavior can be obtained by the modified one. From this result, our concern was whether or not there is a factor having an effect on the agent's learning except for the past information reference.

For realizing the settings that is close to the real environment, Shirasaki and Sato [7] adopted a neural Q-learning [8] (NQL) that can treat continuous quantity of input information. The NQL agents have feedforward type neural networks (FFNN) that are used as estimating systems of their Q-values for Q-learning,

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and we compare the performances of the Q-learning and the NQL agents. The simulation results in our previous work [7] illustrated that the NQL agents whose memory size is 1 showed the high performance in the task of arriving at the goals than those of the Q-learning agents, but as the maximum numbers of the learning iterations and the memory sizes are increased, the performance of the NQL agents fell to an extremely low level. As the reason for these, we think there are two problems: One is that the FFNN cannot appropriately learn a time-series data with temporal structures. The other is that the inconsistencies in the data come to occur easily by increasing the past information that the FFNN received. However, from a viewpoint that the time structure of current language is one of the important features, we think that learning data with time structures is very important for emerging communication.

In accord with the above back ground, we hypothesize that the communication can be established by the following process; “actions” having some purposes would be used as “symbols” on the communication through the learning process of a time-series of action primitives and the interactions between opponents in their life courses.

The purpose of this study is to discuss the requirements of the reinforcement learning agents suitable for analyzing the emergence of communication and for verifying our hypothesis and to clarify its necessary factors. To achieve the purpose, we adopt recurrent Q-learning [8][9] (RQL) agents that can learn continuous quantity of input information with time structures and employ the collision avoidance game similar to the model of Takano and Arita [3].

II. COLLISION AVOIDANCE GAME

In our simulation, we use a multi-agent system based on the model of Takano and Arita [3], because it is suitable for verifying our hypothesis in which “actions” with certain purposes can be used as “symbols” on the communication. In the multi-agent system of our study, many agents are randomly placed in two dimensional continuous space surrounded by the wall and aimed to attain their goals from each starting point as soon as possible. When the agent collides with its opponents, the movement velocity of the agent at next step is decreased drastically. Because of that, the agent is required not only to approach to its goal but also to expect the behavior of the nearest neighbor

agent and to avoid collision with the others. After the agent arrived at its goal, its new goal is randomly replaced. We named the game “Collision Avoidance Game.” The schematic view of the game is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Schematic view of a collision avoidance game and information given to the agents.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the agent used in our simulation have a fan shape type eyesight, R , face type two wheels, and can move its eyesight from side to side. The agent moves by receiving the following eight information; the goal (d_g, θ_g), the angle of direction of its eye (Φ), the nearest agent in own eyesight ($d_a, \theta_a, \alpha, \beta$), and wall (d_w), where d_g is the distance of the goal, θ_g is the angle of the goal to the direction of movement, α is the angle of direction of the nearest neighbor agent's movement to the direction that the agent watched opponent, β is the angle of direction of the nearest neighbor agent's eyesight to the direction that the agent watched opponent, and d_w is the distance of the nearest neighbor wall.

Depending on the above inputs, the agent outputs an angular velocity, $\Delta\Phi(t)$, and two wheels' tread velocities, $w_r(t)$ and $w_l(t)$, where $w_r(t)$ and $w_l(t)=0.1$ or 1.0 , $-\pi/2 < \Phi \leq \pi/2$, $\Delta\Phi = -\pi/50.0, 0.0, \text{ or } \pi/50.0$. The agent's directions of its movement and eye at next step are calculated based on $w_r(t)$ and $w_l(t)$ as the following formulas.

$$\phi(t+1) = \phi(t) + \Delta\phi(t) \quad (1)$$

$$m(t+1) = m(t) + \frac{w_r(t) - w_l(t)}{2r} \quad (2)$$

Where m is the direction of movement, r is the radius of the agent. The migration velocity of the agent, v , is calculated as below.

$$v(t) = \frac{w_r(t) + w_l(t)}{2} \quad (3)$$

where v is given the following cost, depending on the size of Φ .

$$v(t) = v(t)(-c|\phi| + 1) \quad (4)$$

where c is the size of cost ($c \geq 0$), and also v is set to 0 when $v < 0$. We can hereby give the following two costs; one is the explicit cost that the migration velocity decreases depending on the measure of the angle of movement direction away from the direction of eye, and the other is the implicit cost that the agent becomes difficult to realize the appropriate collision avoidance behavior because the agent becomes difficult to bring the others into its sight by turning its sight away from other agents. Moreover, the velocity of the agent's movement at the next step is drastically decreased when colliding with the others. Each agent's coordinates at the next step, $x(t+1)$ and $y(t+1)$, are given by the following formulas.

$$x(t + 1) = x(t) + v(t) \cos m(t + 1) \quad (5)$$

$$y(t + 1) = y(t) + v(t) \sin m(t + 1) \quad (6)$$

Next, we explain the learning methods. In a situation in which symbols and forms used in a communication are not established, we assume that the agent obtains a way of communicating with opponents by trial and error. Also there is a possibility that the differences of the important states to achieve the aim can be overlooked in case of discretizing the environment information and that the time-series learning ability is important to establish a communication system. Based on the above explanations, we adopt the recurrent Q-learning [8][9] (RQL) which is the hybridization between two systems; one is the Q-learning [5], the other is the recurrent neural network [10] (RNN).

The Q-learning [5] is one of the reinforcement learning method by trial and error. In accordance with the following equation, the agents with the Q-learning renew the Q-values representing the worth of the agents' actions for each state at the environment, and obtain more appropriate behaviors.

$$Q(s(t), a(t)) := Q(s(t), a(t)) + \eta_Q [rw(t + 1) + \gamma \max_a Q(s(t + 1), a) - Q(s(t), a(t))] \quad (7)$$

where $a(t)$ is an action conducted at time t , $Q(s(t), a(t))$ is a Q-value for an action conducted under a state s at time t , η_Q is the learning rate, $rw(t+1)$ is a reward given from the environment when conducting an action under a state s , and γ is the discount rate.

The RNN [10] is a learning model simulated features of the human brains. This model can treat and learn continuous values with time structures as inputs from the environment. In this study, we adopt the simple recurrent network (SRN) which has a context layer and recurrent connections from the hidden layer to the input layer and was proposed by Elman [11], as illustrated in Fig. 2. Each context neuron in the context layer of the SRN has one-for-one connections with each hidden neuron in order to copy previous activation values of the hidden neurons.

Fig. 2 A procedure for the recurrent Q-learning.

We can consider the context layer as a type of input layer at each time step, because the network can be regarded as a kind of feedforward type neural network [10]. Therefore, as a learning method, we adopt the normal back-propagation (BP) learning [10] toward the SRN. The weights of all recurrent connections between the hidden and the context layers are fixed to 1.0 and are not adjusted by learning.

In the RQL [8][9], the observed data (continuous data) of the environment as the input are given to the SRN first. Next, the Q-values for each action corresponding to all output neurons is gotten from the SRN. Finally, the agents get rewards after conducting

their actions based on the Q-values. The teacher signals are generated by using the following equation.

$$T(s(t), a(t)) := rw(t + 1) + \gamma \max_a Q(s(t + 1), a) \quad (8)$$

where $T(s(t), a(t))$ is the renewed Q-value for the action conducted under a state s at time t and is also a teacher signal used for the BP learning of the SRN. Except for the valuables explained here, the remained ones of the equation(8) are the same as the valuables of equation(7). The agents learn to be able to presume more appropriate Q-values by using the teacher signals. The ϵ -greedy policy [5] is adopted as the way of selecting actions. A procedure of the RQL is shown in Fig. 2. The numbers in Fig. 2 mean the order of processing.

In this study, we compare the performances of the NQL adopted in our previous work [7] and the RQL agents in order to verify the influences of learning ability of time-series inputs.

III. SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS

A. Settings of simulation experiments

The parameters used in the simulation experiments are as follows: The rewards (positive values) and penalties (negative values) giving to the agents are +0.12 when arriving at their goals, -0.01 when colliding with the opponents included the wall, and getting close to the wall. Moreover, the reward given to the agent every step is (the past d_a - the current d_a) \times 0.08. Also -0.03 \times $\pi/2.0 \times |\pi|$ is given to the agent as the penalty when the agent's eye averted from the direction of its movement, and is used for the learning of only output concerning its eye movement. The simulation experiments are conducted in two dimensional continuous space measuring 20 by 20. The number of agents is 3. The collision avoidance game is continuously played until 10000 episodes, where one episode consists of 10000 steps.

The agent is represented by a round shape with a radius r of 0.5, and has an eyesight R which is a fun shape with a radius of 5 and the angle π centered at the eyesight. The cost averted from the direction of the agent's eyesight is 0.5. When the agent came into collision with the opponent, its movement speed at the next step multiplies by 0.05.

Here are the parameters of the reinforcement learning; the probability ϵ to select an action randomly is 0.1, the learning rate η_Q is 0.01, and the discount rate γ is 0.8. Also, the parameters of the SRN are as follow;

the learning rate η_N is 0.01, and the strength of non-linearity λ is 0.8. The learning process of the SRN is completed when the learning error dropped below 0.01. The SRN has eight input neurons, five hidden neurons (i.e., the context neurons are five, too), and seven output neurons. The seven values of the output neurons correspond to four values ($w_r, w_l = 0.1$ or 1.0) for actions to move the agent's two wheels and three values ($\Delta\Phi = -\pi/50.0, 0.0, \text{ or } \pi/50.0$) for actions to move the agent's eye from side to side.

In this study, both neural and recurrent Q-learning agents, whose memory size is 5, have three types of the maximum number of learning iterations (5000, 10000, and 20000). The maximum number of learning iterations is an upper limit of the number to learn all patterns. The memory size is the amount of information for past multiple steps, which the agents learn them every step. We conducted the simulation experiments with ten different kinds of random seeds per six types of agents.

B. Results of simulation experiments

First, as illustrated in Fig. 3, we depict the comparative results of ensemble averages of the number of times arriving at the goals every episode in the NQL and the RQL agents with three types of maximum numbers of learning iterations. Figure 3 shows that the performances of the RQL agents whose the maximum numbers of the learning iterations are 10000 and 20000 are lower than all of that of the NQL agents. We also found that the two kinds of RQL agents fail to increase the number of times arriving at the goals.

Fig. 3 Dynamics of ensemble averages of the number of times arriving at the goals at each episode.

To compare each performance in detail, we confirm ensemble averages of the simulation results for last

1000 episodes in all runs as the results of each agent. In Fig. 4, we found that the performance of the RQL agent whose the maximum number of the learning is 5000 is rarely different from that of the NQL agents, but the RQL agents cannot get better performance with increased times of the learning iteration.

Fig. 4 Ensemble averages of the number of times arriving at the goals for the last 1000 episodes.

Next, as illustrated in Fig. 5, we show the comparative results of ensemble averages of the number of times of collisions with the opponents every episode in the NQL and the RQL agents with three different maximum numbers of the learning iterations. As can be seen, the RQL agents whose the maximum numbers of the learning iterations are 20000 can succeed to learn the way of avoiding collisions with the opponents because their collision times decreased with each passing episode.

Fig. 5 Dynamics of ensemble averages of the number of times colliding with the opponents at each episode.

Let us see ensemble averages of the number of times colliding with the opponents for the last 1000 episodes. Figure 6 illustrates that, as the maximum numbers of the learning iterations increase, the number of times colliding with the opponents in the RQL agents is decreased, as against the performances of the NQL agents are almost the same.

Fig. 6 Ensemble averages of the number of times colliding with the opponents for the last 1000 episodes.

Thirdly, we confirm whether or not symbolization of action primitives to avoid collisions with the opponents emerges in the RQL agents. As the symbolization, two patterns can be thought as illustrated in Fig. 7. One, the pattern 1, is that the directions of the eye and the movement are almost the same, namely, the RQL agent moves to opposite side of the direction of the opponent's movement and eye. This pattern is not special, because there is no cost if the eye and the movement face in the same direction. The other, the pattern 2, is that the RQL agent moves to opposite side of the direction of the opponent's eye. Realizing this pattern is a bit hard, because the RQL agent costs to keep on averting his/her gaze.

Fig. 7 Emergence of two types of communications by action primitives glancing aside to avoid collisions with the opponents as communication signals.

Table 1 shows the correlation coefficients of the RQL agents' inputs and outputs related to two patterns of collision avoidance behaviors. If the correlation coefficient between the direction of the movement and the θ_a is negative, this means that the RQL agents move to the direction moved away from the opponents. If the correlation coefficient between the direction of the movement and the β is positive, this means that the RQL agents move to the direction that the opponents are not watching. If the correlation coefficient between the direction of the movement and the Φ is positive, this means that the RQL agents move to the direction that the oneself are watching. If the correlation coefficient between the $\Delta\Phi$ and β is positive, this means that the RQL agents' sight lines move to the direction that the opponents are not watching. In case that the RQL agent has this combination of correlation coefficients, the RQL agent behaves based on the collision avoidance pattern 1.

Table. 1 Each correlation coefficients of the agents' inputs and outputs related to two patterns of collision avoidance behaviors.

	corr(direction, θ_a)	corr(direction, β)	corr(direction, ϕ)	corr($\Delta\phi$, β)
Pattern 1	-0.158478248	0.216588697	0.305348044	0.199255111
Pattern 2	-0.294776983	-0.245780619	-0.428396122	0.206495912

As can be seen, however, each correlation coefficient is small. That is to say; this means that these collision avoidance patterns are rarely found in our simulations. In actual, we found eight RQL agents moving based on the patterns in thirty RQL agents (the population size 3 times 10 run with different random seeds).

Lastly, we investigate orbits of the RQL agents in detail. As it turned out, we found that the RQL agents obtain rotational motions to avoid collisions with the opponents and to wait until the opponents pass. Figure 8 illustrates difference between the orbits of the RQL agents whose the maximum numbers of the learning iterations are 10 and 20000. In the orbits of the RQL agents whose the maximum numbers of the learning iterations are 10, the agents move linearly and give preference to arriving at their goals over avoiding collision with the opponents. By contrast, in the orbits of the RQL agents whose the maximum numbers of the learning iterations are 20000, the agents show rotational

motions and give preference to avoiding collision with the opponents over arriving at their goals.

Fig. 8 Emergence of rotational motions to avoid collisions with the opponents and the walls and to wait until the opponents pass.

Figure 9 shows exploded views of the rotational motions per 100 steps at the last episode. As can be seen, the RQL agent behave the rotational motion when getting close to the wall, and also the RQL agent rotates when the opponent becomes fairly close to oneself. Moreover, we found that the agent waits until the opponent pass by rotating at almost the same place.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to discuss the requirements of the reinforcement learning agents suitable for analyzing the emergence of communication and for verifying our hypothesis, and to clarify its necessary factors. To achieve the purpose, we adopted recurrent Q-learning (RQL) agents that can learn continuous quantity of input information with time structures and employ the collision avoidance game.

Although there was considerable lowering of the number of arriving at the goals by increasing the maximum number of the learning iteration, the performance of avoiding collision with the opponents was improved inversely. The RQL agents obtained the ability to avoid collision preferentially through the learning process so that the collisions occur predominantly in the game. If the maximum number of the learning iterations and episode for the learning lengthen, or more specifically, the reward function for the recurrent Q-learning changes appropriately, both of performances of arriving at the goals and avoiding collisions can be improved.

Fig. 9 Exploded view of the rotational motions per 100 steps at the last episode.

Moreover, though in rare cases, we found that proto-communication system emerges by the symbolization of the RQL agents' action primitives that the RQL agents move their sight lines. We also confirmed that the RQL agents can obtain the rotational behavior to avoid collision with the opponents and the wall with a probability of 100% in case that the maximum number of the learning iteration is large. Especially, the recurrent neural network's ability to learn time-series inputs is the important factor to realize the rotational motions and to wait until the opponents pass so that the ability can count the number of rotation.

Based on the outcomes of the discussions mentioned above, we conclude that the recurrent Q-learning agents with the learning ability of the time-series inputs are better suited for analyzing the emergent phenomena of communication by gesture and evaluating our hypothesis.

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REFERENCES

[1] M.C. Corballis. *From Hand To Mouth -The Origin of Language-*, Princeton Univ. Press, 2002.
 [2] M. Tomasello. *Origins of Human Communication*, MIT Press, 2008.
 [3] M. Takano and T. Arita. Emergence of communication based on gaze control through the coevolutionary dynamics of mind reading and manipulation of others (in

Japanese), *Proceedings of the 13th MPS Symposium 2006*, pp:203-208, Oct.24-25, 2006, Nagoya.
 [4] F. Shirasaki and T. Sato. Emergence of communication based on agent's action learning in a collision avoidance game (in Japanese), *IPSI SIG Technical Report*, vol.2012-MPS-87, no.29, pp:1-2, 2012.
 [5] R.S. Sutton and A.G. Barto. *Reinforcement Learning: An Introduction*, MIT Press, 1998.
 [6] T. Sato. Germ of communication based on learning history of action primitives (in Japanese), *Journal of the Society of Instrument and Control Engineers*, vol.53, no.9, pp:847-852, 2014.
 [7] F. Shirasaki and T. Sato. A comparative study on the performance of Q-learning and neural Q-learning agents towards analysis of emergence of communication in a collision avoidance game (in Japanese), *Proceedings of the SICE Symposium on Systems and Information 2014 (SSI2014)* (CD-ROM), Nov.21-23, 2014, Okayama.
 [8] L.J. Lin and T.M. Mitchell. Memory approaches to reinforcement learning in non-markovian domains, *Technical Report*, CMU-CS-92-138, Carnegie Mellon University, 1992.
 [9] K. Shibata. Learning of Exploration Behavior by Reinforcement Learning, *Proceedings of the SICE Symposium on Systems and Information 2005 (SSI2005)*, pp:11-16, Nov.28-30, 2005, Fukuoka.
 [10] K. Ito. *Neuro Dynamics* (in Japanese), Kyoritsu Shuppan, 2010.
 [11] J.L. Elman. Finding structure in time, *Cognitive Science*, vol.14, no.2, pp:179-211, 1990.